

Questions, Comments and Answers following the presentation

High-contrast imaging

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Ballester: Could you describe the impact of using a library of PSFs on the SPHERE data reduction?

Classical data reduction is based on a single data set (from a single OB) where for instance angular differential imaging provides the ability to identify and subtract the stellar halo. In addition, a similar data set on a reference star can be used for “reference differential imaging” (RDI). Considering the number of different factors that affect the stellar halo in details (exact settings, quasi-static aberrations depending on many factors like pointing direction, temperature, wind speed, seeing,...), it has been proposed and tried in different cases that references are searched for with better success in a much larger set of star observed in a similar set-up. This approach reaches then a large domain of research (machine learning, deep learning) to try to recognize the best pattern. This has proved very efficient in other domains, and is now under investigation in this topic. Practically this implies to have access to very large data sets when public.

Szentgyorgyi: What are the prospects for coronagraphic detection of earth twins?

This is by now quite far from current performance of direct imaging. However the frequency of low mass planets suggests that they are ubiquitous and present in particular in the most favorable stellar cases, as proven by the case of Prox b. In such favorable case, pushing far the performance of current “SPHERE-like” systems, especially if improving AO and coupling to high resolution spectroscopy (in the visible in the case of Prox b in order to obtain the right angular resolution) may bring the detection and characterization of such earth-twins close to feasibility (see Lovis et al 2016) with 8-m telescopes. It is definitely within the science case for high contrast imaging of ELTs.

Chilingarian: What is the general perspective of high-contrast imaging with the ELTs, which will all have segmented mirrors and, consequently, higher level of scattering?

The foreseen ELT pupils are very unfriendly to high contrast imaging, in comparison to the VLT pupil (or, even better, to unobscured pupils). Segmentation is an issue but not the worst: we assume that proper cophasing can be achieved, and the gaps between segments induce only limited (and localized, and known) diffraction patterns. Another issue is the question of missing segments (either due to random failure, or absence for regular maintenance). This has a strong impact on large areas of the FoV: it can (and should) be addressed by dedicated solutions within coronagraph systems. The largest issue would certainly be the case of a very large central obstruction (primary mirror limited to an annulus) that would send a very large amount of energy in the PSF wings. Very specific

coronagraph designs would then be needed but at a strong cost in terms of transmission and/or inner working angle (see the corresponding studies in the case of the unfriendly pupil of WFIRST).

Ballester: Could you give an indicator of the nature of AO telemetry data to be recorded (statistical, raw data) and the data rate it will imply?

See answer of the next question, providing information to both questions.

Leibundgut: Is the telemetry data of SPHERE used for the calibration and the data reductions?

Currently, AO RTC data are recorded in terms of statistics, with a sparse temporal sampling (typically every minute). This allows to monitor the general correction quality over the night, and this is used by a large number of observers: this is already very useful but this is far from representative of any given science detector image properties.

A (quite easy, I think) important step forward would be to keep the same approach (statistics of WFS measurements and commands to deformable mirror) but with a higher frequency (typically every frequency). This quantitative change would qualitatively enhance significantly the use in order to qualify or guide image selection within data cubes. I would really encourage this step. The data flow is very limited (essentially negligible wrt science data flow).

Another thing would be to record extensively all AO data. The data flow is here significant. Much more information is of course included there but there is no clear demonstration on how this can actually be used to enhance science data reduction. It may be good to record such sequences on a regular basis for specific tests and data analysis before discussing about a systematic archive.